

The Effects of Chinese Investments in Digital Infrastructures on Data Policies and Regulations in Host Countries: A Case Study on New Clark City, Philippines

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Abstract

China's Digital Silk Road is a strategy guide for Chinese technology companies to invest in digital infrastructures in Belt and Road Initiative signatory countries. There is, however, little research about the effects of Chinese-funded digital infrastructures in these countries. This paper examines the impact of Chinese investments in digital infrastructures in smart cities in Southeast Asia on data policies and regulations in host countries. We use New Clark City as a case study. Previously the site of an American airbase in the Philippines, New Clark City is anticipated to be the country's first smart city with Chinese support. Data analysis is made by examining key informant interviews and reviewing policy documents and articles to determine (1) Chinese push and pull factors in transnational data governance, (2) the scale of Chinese-funded digital infrastructures, and (3) the perceptions of Philippine state and non-state actors. We make two implications. First, the transnational flow of ideas, expertise, capital, and technologies involving data provided by Chinese technology companies influenced the Philippines to adopt Chinese data policies and regulations. Second, the same transfer of digital infrastructures also affects the host country to adopt Chinese environmental and energy standards. All these could mean that Southeast Asian smart cities receiving Chinese investments in digital infrastructures, including New Clark City, have their data policies and regulations contain Chinese characteristics.